

*Please note: The application has changed considerably since this was submitted. This is just an example of a research topic in the life sciences that seemingly aligned with the DoD's interests at the time.*

In your own words, provide a summary of your educational program objectives and your long-range professional goals.

As part of this statement, we are interested in your ideas about:

- the kinds of research in which you would like to be engaged during your graduate study or in the longer term; or
- specific research questions that interest you and how you became interested in them.

Please discuss these research interests in sufficient detail for an expert who is technically competent in your field to judge your understanding of the questions to be addressed. This includes relevant hypotheses and approaches one might take to answering the questions, and other research principles required to investigate the research area you identify.

We are interested in not only the science, but also your longer-term goals and how the science fits into your life as an individual. We do not want this to look like a grant submission. Your response will be limited to 3,000 characters, including spaces. There is no extra space for citations.

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Proposed DoD sponsoring agency: Army Research Office (ARO)

Neuroscience captivates me because it is a developing field that unites researchers through their common, human interest in the function of the brain. Just as different neurons in a circuit communicate with one another, biologists, chemists, engineers, physicians, and physicists collaborate on cross-disciplinary projects. I, too, hope to draw from my background in the basic biological sciences to answer questions about the molecular and cellular biology of cognition.

An outstanding question in cell biology is how cells regulate the distribution of mitochondria--the powerhouses of the cell--in response to local energy demands. This is a particularly challenging problem for neurons, as their extended processes rely on proper transport of mitochondria to active synapses. Thus, dynamic regulation of mitochondrial distribution in neurons must integrate metabolic signals that indicate intracellular nutrient availability.

I am rotating in Thomas Schwarz's lab to study how a little-understood reversible posttranslational modification, O-linked N-acetylglucosamine (O-GlcNAc), affects mitochondrial trafficking in axons. This monosaccharide acts as a nutrient sensor because synthesis of its precursor is sensitive to changes in glucose concentration. Remarkably, overexpression of the O-GlcNAc-adding enzyme, O-GlcNAc transferase (OGT), stops mitochondrial movement in axons. The Schwarz lab previously found that OGT binds to OIP106 interacting protein 106 (OIP106), an adaptor that tethers mitochondria to microtubule motor proteins. One could thus imagine that OIP106 in glucose-rich regions of a neuron will be more O-GlcNAcylated and keep mitochondria in areas of high demand.

To test whether O-GlcNAcylation of OIP106 regulates mitochondrial trafficking in axons, I am mapping the OGT-OIP106 interaction using OIP106 constructs with deletions in putative OGT binding regions. I will screen for constructs that disrupt OGT binding by coimmunoprecipitation and transfect them into primary rat hippocampal neurons. As these constructs cannot bind to OGT and thus cannot be O-GlcNAcylated, cotransfection with OGT should rescue the mitochondrial motility lost in OGT-overexpressing neurons.

As defects in mitochondrial transport impair synaptic plasticity, my work could help identify dietary conditions or develop OGT/OIP106-targeting molecules that optimize cognitive performance. They could also lead to treatments for diabetics, as excess glucose could increase mitochondrial O-GlcNAcylation and promote neuropathy. By studying learning and memory processes and diabetic neuropathy in OGT and OIP106 knockout mice, I hope to improve the quality of life of both healthy individuals and diabetics.

I am fascinated by research questions that lie at the interface of molecular and cell biology and neuroscience because of their broad impacts. With the NDSEG Fellowship I will continue my Ph.D. training at Harvard in the Schwarz lab, and work toward my goal of becoming a neurobiology professor.